

ISic3684

I.Sicily inscription 3684

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

marble

Object

fragment

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Melita

Place of origin (modern)

Malta

Provenance

found in cistern of the monastery of S. Pietro nella Notabile

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Malta

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140929

1. [— —] Βελλ(—) □ Ἑρμῆς [— —]
2. [— —]ΤΩΑΡΧ [— — — — —]
- 3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

PHI 140929

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio*

et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV. Berlin.
At 14.0602 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

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